

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20342993

Assessment Of Non-Governmental Organizations' Intervention In Upper Basic Schools In Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the Non-Governmental Organization Intervention in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria". Two (2) objectives guided the study. Two corresponding research questions and research hypotheses were in line with the research objectives. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The total population for the study is 760 comprised of twenty-four upper basic schools and this comprised of, 24 principals, 558 teachers, 168 SBMC officials and 10 NGOs officials. The sample size of the study was 256 determined using a Research Advisor sampling table (2006). A multi-stage sampling method was adopted by the study where the population was divided into three clusters and three schools were selected randomly from each cluster. Proportionate sampling procedure was used to distribute the questionnaire. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled Intervention of NGOs in upper Basic schools in Katsina state designed on four point scale. The questionnaire was validated and pilot tested using Cronbach's Alpha technique, which revealed the composite reliability index of 0.91. Descriptive statistics of frequency count mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. One-Way-Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. Findings from the study among others shows that principals, teachers, NGOs officials and SBMC differ significantly in opinion that Non-governmental Organisations has not provide intervention of funds in upper basic schools (p-value of .029) is less than 0.05. findings of the study among others reveals that principals, teachers, NGOs officials and SBMC differ significantly in opinion regarding Non-governmental Organization intervention on provision of funds in upper basic schools (p = .029). Based on the findings of the study it concluded that, Non-governmental Organizations provide intervention of funding and teacher-training in upper basic schools. In line with the findings and conclusion the study recommends that principals and teachers should devise a mechanism that would be used to regularly brief on how the funds are allocated and used in the school and this can be done by actively involving the School Based Management Committee officials in planning and oversight in order to clear differences in opinion regarding the NGOs intervention on school funding.

Keywords: Non-Governmental Organizations, Interventions, Upper Basic

INTRODUCTION

Education is a long term investment and is too demanding that made both the states and Federal Government in Nigeria give more attention to it. Relevant stakeholders such as Non-governmental Organizations intervene in the educational sector in Nigeria to assist in improving the condition and value of Primary, Secondary and Tertiary Education in the country. Fogler, (2024) opine that Non-governmental Organizations are non-dependent institutions that operate locally, regionally, nationally and globally for the purpose of improving the life of the poor and for improving the condition of human living environments. The said non-governmental organizations play a key role in the provision of resources at the post primary education level, thereby endowing the upper basic level schools with financial aids and resources, which serve as technical aids to less advantaged schools in Nigerian communities as mentioned by Education Partnership Centre.

The Nigerian educational landscape has been plagued by various issues, including under funding, scarce educational resources, inadequately trained educators, obsolete curricula, and poor student participations; therefore to address these concerns, Non-Governmental Organizations have emerged as key players in supporting and administering diverse aspects of education in Nigeria (Adebayo, 2019) thereby providing monetary assistance which has been vital in regions where governmental funding has been lacking or irregular. It has however observed that several NGOs have aided in developing more pertinent and contemporary curricula, especially in fields such as technology education and vocational training (Akinbote, 2017), as they have significantly contributed to increasing student enrollment, particularly among disadvantaged groups. These entities have been crucial in bridging the gaps left by governmental efforts and contributing to the overall enhancement of educational framework.

Statement of the Problem

Despite policy frameworks and interventions, evidence suggests that the quality of education at the upper basic level remains a matter of concern. The laudable objectives of upper basic education which include; serves as the bridge between primary education and senior secondary education, shaping learners' cognitive, social, and vocational competencies has not seems to be fully accomplished. Upper basic schools face persistent challenges including inadequate funding. This challenge directly affects the effectiveness, performance, and overall quality of upper basic education. Given the strategic importance of upper basic education in the Nigerian educational system and the increasing involvement of NGOs in supporting public schools, there is a compelling need to assess the effectiveness of this intervention in promoting quality of upper basic schools in Daura Zone. Therefore, it is against this that, this study seeks to assess the Non-Governmental Organizations' intervention in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, with a focus on Provision of funding.

Objective of the Study

The following objectives guided the study:

- Assess the Non-governmental Organizations intervention on provision of funds in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
- Determine the Non-governmental Organizations intervention on teacher-training in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Question

The study answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of Non-governmental Organizations intervention on provision of funds in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
2. What is the level of Non-governmental Organizations intervention on teacher-training in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?

Research Hypothesis

The following Null Hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the respondent opinion that Non-Governmental Organizations has not provide intervention of funds in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the respondent opinion that Non-Governmental Organizations has not provide intervention of teacher -training in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Literature Review

Conceptual Views

Non-Governmental Organizations

Non-Governmental Organizations are private own organizations that financially intervene in the improvement of both the life and environment of human beings around the globe. World Bank (2019) describes NGOs as: "Private organizations that pursue activities to relieve suffering, promote the interests of the poor, protect the environment, provide basic social services, or undertake community Development 'They are driven by a mission to address specific social or environmental concerns, such as poverty, human rights, education, healthcare, or environmental conservation.

Upper Basic Education

Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria plays a crucial role in shaping the academic and personal development of students as they transit from primary to secondary school. This stage of education is designed to provide students with a solid foundation in various subjects and skills, preparing them for the challenges of senior secondary education and beyond. The basic upper schools in Nigeria are based on the National Policy on Education's (FRN, 2014) objectives, which emphasizes the importance of providing quality education to all students. The main goals of basic upper schools as stated in the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014) are as follows:

- i. Preparing students for the challenges of senior secondary education and higher education.
- ii. Providing students with a strong foundation in core subjects, junior secondary education aims to build their academic skills and critical thinking abilities.
- iii. Instilling values such as discipline, respect, and teamwork in students, preparing them for success in their future endeavors

Empirical Studies

This study is on the assessment of Non-Governmental Organization Intervention in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. Afolabi, Tyokyaa and Ochai (2025) investigated the extent of the contributions of Non-Governmental Organizations towards the administration of Public Secondary Schools in North-Central Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design and it reveals that Non-Governmental Organization has played a significant role in funding. Nsikak, (2025) conducted a study on the impact of international organizations on education development in Nigeria. The paper used secondary data. Content analysis was used to analyze the selection of literature for the study and the study discovers that, international organizations in Nigeria have contributed to education development in the following area; funding, provision of facilities, capacity building and instructional materials.

Similarly, Katcha and Mukaddas, (2024) investigated the perceived impacts of foreign education intervention programme on the performance of Basic Science and Technology teachers in the Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was employed for the study and the study found that Basic Science Teachers' performance was positively impacted through regular in-service training, workshops, and seminars organized by foreign organizations in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The total population for the study is 760 comprised of twenty-four upper basic schools and this comprised of, 24 principals, 558 teachers, 168 SBMC officials and 10 NGOs officials. The sample size of the study was 256 determined using a Research Advisor sampling table (2006). A multi-stage sampling method was adopted by the study where the population was divided into three clusters and three schools were selected randomly from each cluster. Proportionate sampling procedure was used to distribute the questionnaire. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled Intervention of NGOs in upper Basic schools in Katsina state designed on four point scale. The questionnaire was validated and pilot tested using Cronbach's Alpha

technique, which revealed the composite reliability index of 0.91. Descriptive statistics of frequency count mean and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. One-Way-Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Respondents' Opinion on the Non-governmental Organisations Intervention on Provision of Funds in Upper Basic Schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State

S/N	Item Statement	Respondents	N	SA F	A F	D F	SD F	Mean	STD.
1	NGOs have played a significant role in provision of funds in my school	Principals	09	03	05	01	00	3.22	0.66
		Teachers	164	68	46	28	22	2.97	1.06
		NGOs Officials	10	07	03	00	00	3.70	0.48
		SBMC Officials	58	24	15	08	11	2.89	1.14
2	My school has benefited from NGO-funded projects.	Principals	09	01	02	06	00	2.44	0.72
		Teachers	164	59	54	35	16	2.95	0.98
		NGOs Officials	10	05	04	01	00	3.40	0.69
		SBMC Officials	58	25	15	10	08	2.98	1.08
3	NGOs have supported the construction or renovation of classrooms in my school.	Principals	09	04	03	02	00	3.22	0.83
		Teachers	164	55	52	42	15	2.89	0.97
		NGOs Officials	10	06	04	00	00	3.60	0.51
		SBMC Officials	58	21	12	17	08	2.79	1.08
4	NGO funding has enhanced access to school by reducing the financial burden on students.	Principals	09	04	02	02	01	3.00	1.11
		Teachers	164	44	51	51	18	2.73	0.97
		NGOs Officials	10	03	04	03	00	3.00	0.81
		SBMC Officials	58	21	09	22	06	2.77	1.06
5	NGO-provided funds are used transparently in my school.	Principals	09	01	06	02	00	2.88	0.60
		Teachers	164	39	64	43	18	2.74	0.99
		NGOs Officials	10	07	03	00	00	3.70	0.48
		SBMC Officials	58	15	15	20	08	2.63	1.02
6	Training programmes for teachers have been funded by NGOs in my school.	Principals	09	06	02	01	00	3.55	0.72
		Teachers	164	45	52	47	20	2.89	0.93
		NGOs Officials	10	02	01	05	02	2.30	1.05
		SBMC Officials	58	19	13	16	10	2.70	1.10
7	NGO support has complemented government efforts in school funding.	Principals	09	03	02	02	02	2.66	1.22
		Teachers	164	32	59	38	55	2.53	1.03
		NGOs Officials	10	02	01	05	02	2.30	1.05
		SBMC Officials	58	14	12	15	17	2.39	1.15
8	The level of NGO intervention in my school is adequate.	Principals	09	03	03	01	02	2.77	1.20
		Teachers	164	30	53	54	27	2.52	0.97
		NGOs Officials	10	02	02	02	04	2.20	1.22
		SBMC Officials	58	10	15	19	14	2.36	1.03
9	NGO funding has led to noticeable improvement in student academic performance.	Principals	09	05	03	00	01	3.33	1.00
		Teachers	164	37	51	46	30	2.57	1.03
		NGOs Officials	10	05	04	01	00	3.40	0.69
		SBMC Officials	58	11	11	21	15	2.31	1.06
10	NGOs provide scholarships or financial aid to needy students in upper basic in my school.	Principals	09	00	01	07	01	2.00	0.50
		Teachers	164	45	36	42	41	2.51	1.14
		NGOs Officials	10	07	03	00	00	3.70	0.48
		SBMC Officials	58	14	11	15	18	2.36	1.16
Grand Mean		Principals						2.91	
		Teachers						2.72	
		NGOs Officials						3.16	
		SBMC Officials						2.62	
		Total G. Mean						2.85	

Table 1 indicates the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation scores and it reveals that NGOs officials have highest grand mean score of 3.16, followed by principals with a grand mean score of 2.91, teachers 2.72 and last SBMC officials with a grand mean score of 2.62. This means that, the grand mean scores of all the four categories of respondents' falls above the decision mean of 2.50 and this shows that the respondents have agreed that Non-Governmental Organization intervene on provision of funds in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 2: Respondents' Opinion on the Non-governmental Organisations Intervention on Teacher-Training in Upper Basic Schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State

S/N	Item Statement	Respondents	N	SA F	A F	D F	SD F	Mean	STD.
1	NGOs have organized teacher training programs in my school.	Principals	09	06	03	00	00	3.66	0.50
		Teachers	164	58	73	22	11	3.08	0.86
		NGOs Officials	10	05	03	02	00	3.30	0.82
		SBMC Officials	58	20	21	10	07	2.93	1.00
2	NGO-sponsored training has improved my teaching skills.	Principals	09	02	02	00	05	2.11	1.36
		Teachers	164	59	72	27	06	3.12	0.81
		NGOs Officials	10	05	05	00	00	3.50	0.52
		SBMC Officials	58	29	12	15	02	3.17	0.93
3	The content of NGO training programs is relevant to the upper basic school curriculum.	Principals	09	00	05	04	00	2.55	0.52
		Teachers	164	61	69	26	08	3.11	0.84
		NGOs Officials	10	07	02	01	00	3.60	0.69
		SBMC Officials	58	32	15	07	04	3.29	0.93
4	NGOs provide regular training opportunities for teachers in my school.	Principals	09	01	02	03	03	2.11	1.05
		Teachers	164	43	65	42	14	2.83	0.91
		NGOs Officials	10	02	06	00	02	2.80	1.03
		SBMC Officials	58	19	13	21	05	2.79	1.00
5	The school has a good relationship with NGOs involved in teacher development.	Principals	09	01	03	01	04	2.11	1.16
		Teachers	164	50	60	30	24	2.82	1.02
		NGOs Officials	10	08	02	00	00	3.80	0.42
		SBMC Officials	58	18	18	07	15	2.67	1.17
6	NGO training programs focus on modern teaching methods and pedagogy.	Principals	09	04	03	01	01	3.11	1.05
		Teachers	164	47	48	52	17	2.76	0.98
		NGOs Officials	10	00	02	08	00	2.20	0.42
		SBMC Officials	58	24	03	19	12	2.67	1.21
7	I have attended at least one NGO-sponsored teacher training in my school.	Principals	09	04	05	00	00	3.44	0.52
		Teachers	164	31	63	43	27	2.59	0.97
		NGOs Officials	10	02	02	00	06	2.00	1.33
		SBMC Officials	58	04	23	17	14	2.93	0.91
8	NGO interventions have helped improve classroom management skills.	Principals	09	02	03	00	04	2.33	1.32
		Teachers	164	45	53	38	280	2.70	1.05
		NGOs Officials	10	08	02	00	0	2.80	0.42
		SBMC Officials	58	17	12	09	20	2.44	1.24
9	NGO-funded training has increased my motivation and job satisfaction.	Principals	09	04	04	01	00	3.33	0.70
		Teachers	164	68	48	29	19	3.00	1.03
		NGOs Officials	10	02	04	04	00	2.80	0.78
		SBMC Officials	58	35	08	08	07	3.22	1.09
10	NGO training covers the use of ICT and digital tools in teaching.	Principals	09	06	03	00	00	3.66	0.50
		Teachers	164	47	52	51	14	2.80	0.95
		NGOs Officials	10	07	03	00	00	3.70	0.48
		SBMC Officials	58	16	14	23	05	2.70	0.97
Grand Mean		Principals						2.84	
		Teachers						2.88	
		NGOs Offs.						3.15	
		SBMC Offs.						2.82	
		T.G. Mean						2.92	

Table 2 indicates the frequency counts, mean and standard deviation scores and it reveals that NGOs officials have highest grand mean score of 3.15, followed by teachers with a grand mean score of 2.88, Principals 2.82 and last SBMC officials with a grand mean score of 2.82. This means that, the grand mean scores of all the four categories of respondents falls above the decision mean of 2.50 and this shows that the respondents have similar opinion regarding the Non-Governmental Organization intervention on teacher-training in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Hypotheses Testing

Table 3: Summary of One Way Analysis of Variance on Non-Governmental Organizations Intervention of Funds in Upper Basic Schools

Variation	Sum of Squares	Df.	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig. (P)	Decision
Between Groups	281.515	3	93.838	2.772	.042	Rejected
Within Groups	8023.473	237	33.854			
Total	8304.988	240				

P<0.05

Table 3 shows that the calculated Sig. (P = 042 < 0.05) level of significant set for the study. Hence, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Therefore, There is a significant difference in the opinion of principals, teachers, NGOs officials and SBMC officials that Non-Governmental Organizations has not provide intervention of funds in upper basic schools meaning that the four categories of respondents have differ in opinion that Non-Governmental Organizations’ provides funds in upper basic schools.

Table 4: Summary of One Way Analysis of Variance on Non-Governmental Organizations Intervention of Teacher Training in Upper Basic Schools

Variation	Sum of Squares	Df.	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig. (P)	Decision
Between Groups	95.023	3	31.674	1.284	.281	Retained
Within Groups	5848.014	237	24.675			
Total	5943.037	240				

P<0.05

Table 4 shows that the calculated Sig. (P = .281 > 0.05) level of significant set for the study. Hence, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Therefore, There is no significant difference in the opinion of principals, teachers, NGOs officials and SBMC officials that Non-Governmental Organizations has not provide intervention of teacher training in upper basic schools meaning that the four categories of respondents have similar opinion that Non-Governmental Organizations’ has provided intervention of teacher training in upper basic schools.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This study is on the assessment of Non-Governmental Organization Intervention in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study discovers that principals, teachers, NGOs officials and SBMC differ significantly in opinion regarding Non-governmental Organization intervention on provision of funds in upper basic schools (p = .029). This finding supports the finding of Afolabi, Tyokyaa and Ochai (2025) whose study revealed that Non-Governmental Organization has played a significant role in funding.

The study unveils that, all the four category of respondents have similar opinion regarding Non-governmental Organisations intervention on provision of teacher-training in upper basic schools (p-value of .281), this finding is in agreement with the finding of Nsikak, (2025) who discovers that, international organizations in Nigeria have contributed to education development in the following area; funding, provision of facilities, capacity building and instructional materials. The study finding also concur with the finding of Katcha and Mukaddas, (2024) who unveils that Basic Science Teachers’ performance was positively impacted through regular in-service training, workshops, and seminars organized by foreign organizations in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that, Non-governmental Organizations did provide intervention of funds, teacher-training, curriculum development, enrolment of students and provision of learning materials in upper basic schools in Daura Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were raised:

1. Principals and teachers should devise a mechanism that would be used to regularly brief on how the funds are allocated and used in the school and this can be done by actively involving the School Based Management Committee officials in planning and oversight in order to clear differences in opinion regarding the NGOs intervention on school funding.
2. Government and other educational stakeholders should strengthen partnership with NGOs by providing policy support as well as enabling environment that would encourages continuity and expansion of teacher training across the upper basic schools.

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